

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: GEORGE****FIRST NAME: LIZETTE****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 01****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did not use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: Microsoft Office 365 - MSWord on Windows 10

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Writing an Effective Academic Essay (EUCLID 2021, 7-14)
2. Correct Usage of Punctuation Marks (EUCLID 2021, 15-23)
3. Differentiation Between US & UK English (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
4. Avoiding Plagiarism Pitfalls (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
5. Determining an Appropriate Writing Style (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)
6. Adopting the Chicago Style (EUCLID 2021, 43-57)
7. Understanding Latin Abbreviations & Expressions (EUCLID 2021, 58-64)

FUNDAMENTALS OF EFFECTIVE WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

When I decided to undertake post-graduate doctoral studies, I knew research and writing would be essential to any program I pursued. I also recognized that most education institutes offered writing courses as prerequisites for continuing programs. Similarly, the doctoral degree program in International Law and Treaty Law (DILT) offers an International Academic Writing course (ACA - 401D), which provides basics in essay writing skills and styles, as well as differentiation in US and UK English, among other things (EUCLID 2021, 3).

In this response paper, I will provide an overview of the topics covered in the first period of this course. I will also explain how the material impacted me and led me to re-evaluate and enhance my writing skills. As such, I anticipate that my knowledge and understanding of the dynamics of writing will further hone my research, analytics, and reporting (writing) skills.

The ACA-401D course pack is a beneficial tool (along with the other study material) that I will utilize as my foundational reference for this response paper and subsequent assignments.

2) WRITING AN EFFECTIVE ESSAY

In my profession, I am required to research, analyze, and write various policies, programs, and operational documents. As I considered the methodological approaches used, I realized the similarities of the various types of papers. For instance, my team and I take a very in-depth approach to developing policy documents to generate solutions [answers] to address societal problems and issues. First, we determine the purpose and scope of the policy by identifying the issues and assessing the need for an approach and a possible outcome. Secondly, we gather the necessary data (through research, surveys, consultation, etc.) for analysis. Finally, we develop the policy using the information collected from our research sources.

Similarly, in academic writing, I recall steps taken first to identify a topic of interest, which formed a hypothesis. We conducted the required research and analysis of relevant data, compiled vital information, and generated an appropriate outline based on the topic and information gathered. Once I developed a design, I drafted ideas based on the issues outlined while verifying with details from research.

The ACA-401D course pack provides some basic steps to academic writing, including research, reports, and fieldwork which may or may not be published in various forms (EUCLID 2021, 7). It is clear to me that (similar to policy writing), this systemic approach aims to communicate ideas based on research evidence that provides answers [hypothesis] generated from questions.

I agree with the approach outlined in the ACA-401D course pack that an early start is essential as it allows time to read, research, think, and write. In-depth reading and research will help develop a thesis for analysis based on the knowledge and evidence gathered (EUCLID 2021, 7-8). Additionally, study aids are key in creating a well-thought-through and clearly outlined draft with the following characteristics: a well-defined introduction providing the thesis and roadmap, a structured body detailing key points for addressing the thesis, and a conclusive statement summarizing the main points (EUCLID 2021, 7-11).

The key to effective essay writing is clearly outlining and articulating the answers to questions [theses] and addressing arguments posed with appropriate referencing of the relevant sources of evidence (EUCLID 2021, 11).

3) CORRECT USAGE OF PUNCTUATION MARKS

I remember as early as primary school when I was taught the use of punctuation marks in sentence structure. Over the years, my understanding evolved, although I

sometimes overused a comma or two here and there. In my experience, I found that, unlike published writing, the excessive use of commas within my speeches proved helpful in identifying pauses and opportunities to take a breath in the middle of sentences. Another of my most significant challenges was determining what, when, and where to place punctuation appropriately. However, I gained more clarity from studying the ACA-401D course pack on the use of colon and semi-colon as follows: colon is used for introducing a list of sub-clauses, and a semi-colon, is used to link related parts of a sentence.

The ACA-401D course pack provides further insight into the general rules for the functions and usage of punctuation marks in various forms, including; apostrophes to indicate possession or where a letter is missing, square [for academic writing], curly [for technical purposes] and round brackets for providing additional information; dashes and hyphens used to link words and concepts; quotation marks for identifying direct speech or quote from another source; ellipsis used in the place of omitted text, as well as those punctuation marks [full stop, exclamation, and question mark], which are commonly used to complete sentences (EUCLID 2021, 16-23).

4) DIFFERENTIATION BETWEEN US AND UK ENGLISH

I used the US English style of writing during my early education. However, once I started working in public service, I was required to write UK English (the Queen's English). While I consider myself a quick learner, I sometimes found it challenging to consistently use the US and UK English languages throughout my writing. This challenge also came from the fact that, while I was required to write Government policies, documents, and internal correspondences in UK English, external communications to the private sector were written in US English as the preferred language.

Both variants of 'World English' are highlighted in the ACA-401D course pack and provide differentiation, as well as indicate educated and scientific similarities. Such differences and similarities are identified in pronunciation with the same spelling; spelling with the same pronunciation; same term with different but similar spelling and pronunciation; and same words but different or additional meanings (EUCLID 2021, 25-27). There are also differentiations in grammar, syntax, pronunciation, general, and other common usages, as well as with SBE large collective nouns and SBE pluralized adjectives (EUCLID 2021, 25-27).

It is also important to note the inconsistency in the language in the ACA-401D course pack heading *Differences in Usage with SBE 'Pluralised Adjectives.'* (EUCLID 2021, 27). However, I am not certain if it was intentionally so for this exercise.

5) AVOIDING PLAGIARISM PITFALLS

In today's world, access to information is simply a click of a mouse, as most people would know. Such access makes it easy to cut and paste information from sources and include it in our own material. While that may be possible, the plagiarism pitfall is

determining when, where, and how we need to acknowledge the source. Using such information without crediting the author or creator from whom the information is taken is considered plagiarism and therefore deemed unethical (EUCLID 2021, 34).

I will be the first to admit that in my earlier years [when I did not know better], I engaged in such plagiarism pitfalls, where I copied and pasted information, artwork, quotes, and other types of material for personal use and neglected to give credit to the sources. I am grateful to God that I was spared the embarrassment, as it was for my personal use and not for publication or grading, or else I might have suffered the consequences.

The ACA-401D course pack provides examples of and solutions to avoiding plagiarism. Examples of works that require acknowledgment of sources include quotes, paraphrases, statistics/data, or visuals (such as graphs, art, etc.), all of which need proper citation [in-text & list of works] of the author and sources from which the information was taken (EUCLID 2021, 34-35).

Some people [including me at times] find it much easier to use quotation than paraphrase, as it reduces the brain activity required to retain ideas and information from one source and reproduce them into my format. However, it is clearly stated in the ACA-401D course pack that the best approach is to limit quotations unless used for emphasis or by influential authority.

6) DETERMINING AN APPROPRIATE WRITING STYLE

As a writer, consistency in my writing style is key to ensuring the effective delivery of written output. The ACA-401D course pack (in which EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian)) provides a style guide as a means of documenting basic rules and features of writing that will allow for coherent and consistent publication.

a) ADOPTING THE CHICAGO STYLE

I have registered for a subscription online to *The Chicago Manual of Style Online*, which is touted to be “the venerable, time-tested guide to style, usage, and grammar in an accessible online format. It is the indispensable reference for writers, editors, proofreaders, indexers, copywriters, designers, and publishers, informing the editorial canon with sound, definitive advice” (University of Chicago, 2017)

7) UNDERSTANDING LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

This section of the ACA-401D course pack provides an understanding of the usage of abbreviated words and phrases. This knowledge is essential in my profession, as I use abbreviations in all forms of communication, including speech and writing. At times I try my best to be mindful of my readers [in business, formal, and technical fora] and would decide whether to use or not, given their level of knowledge of the abbreviated words or

phrases. However, after reviewing the ACA-401D course pack, I will endeavor to communicate appropriately using the English equivalent of such abbreviations.

8) **CONCLUSION**

While I consider myself a reasonably good writer, this course study has been helpful in my understanding of idiosyncrasies in my writing. I sometimes reflect and think back to my school days, when I had the opportunity, as a young girl, to learn the essential elements of math and the English language. I took such learning for granted as a youth instead of focusing and primarily relying on that foundation to build the rest of my life and livelihood. I appreciate the value of education as it is essential to our lives as productive persons in society.

This period helped hone my skills to increase my knowledge of the dynamics of writing. I have developed a newfound appreciation for writing, as it requires a well-defined and developed thesis, well-outlined and formatted structure, and well-written work.

I have fully engaged the ACA-401D course pack as required, downloaded and saved all of the templates, interacted with the videos [Grammarly & Zotero], initialized my reference tools to ensure effective writing and adequate citation and referencing of my response papers, quizzes, and major papers.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

The University of Chicago. 2017. "The Chicago Style Manual Online." Accessed May 1, 2023. <https://www.chicagomanualofstyle.org/home.html>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.